

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LONG-TERM RESULTS OF VARIOUS VOLUMES OF SURGICAL INTERVENTION FOR MULTINODULAR EUTHYROID GOITER

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to evaluate the long-term results of various volumes of surgical intervention for multinodular euthyroid goiter.

Material and methods: The study involved 281 patients with multinodular euthyroid goiter (MNEG) who underwent surgical treatment. Of these, 76 (27.1%) patients with bilateral MNEG underwent total thyroidectomy, 72 (25.6%) with bilateral MNEG underwent subtotal thyroidectomy, 35 (12.5%) with bilateral MNEG underwent Dunhill operation (OD), 52 (18.5%) with unilateral MNEG and 46 (16.4%) with nodular euthyroid goiter (NEG) underwent hemithyroidectomy. The age of the patients ranged from 20 to 77 years. Among them, 254 (90.4%) were women and 27 (9.6%) were men.

Results: The recurrence rate after subtotal thyroidectomy was 23.6%, after Dunhill operation was 11.4%, and after hemithyroidectomy was 11.5%. The quality of life for patients after hemithyroidectomy was significantly better: 78.8% of individuals with MNEG did not require the burden of constant hormonal therapy. Postoperative hypothyroidism was noted in 21.2% of patients who underwent hemithyroidectomy for unilateral MNEG. Patients in this group received a minimally reduced dose of levothyroxine compared to other groups of individuals (40.9 ± 5.1 mcg) ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusions Thus, performing hemithyroidectomy for unilateral MNEG represents the optimal volume of surgical intervention. However, the final choice of procedure should be a joint decision between the surgeon and the patient, made with consideration of individual risk factors for recurrence and postoperative hypothyroidism.

Keywords: multinodular euthyroid goiter, thyroidectomy, hemithyroidectomy, hypothyroidism, recurrence.

One of the essential methods for treating nodular pathology is surgery, which has been refined in recent years with the introduction of new technologies and has become safer. The concept of nodular goiter involves the presence of nodules in the thyroid gland (TG) tissue, either a single nodule (uninodular) or several nodules (multinodular), which necessitates the performance of various volumes of surgical intervention. If a single benign nodule is present, hemithyroidectomy (HT) and sufficient completion of the thyroidectomy is considered necessary. For multinodular benign goiter, the question of the volume of surgical intervention remains debatable to this day [2, 3, 5, 6]. Until the end of the last century, subtotal thyroidectomy (ST) was considered the surgery of choice for this pathology. However, the recurrence rate after its performance was high—up to 41.2% [21, 30, 31]. This ultimately prompted surgeons to transition to performing more radical volumes of surgery: total or near-total thyroidectomy (TT) [14, 20, 28]. The subsequent increase in the number of publications related to parathyroid insufficiency [31] and recurrent laryngeal nerve injury [4].

Highlights the serious side effects caused by total thyroidectomy, such as hypocalcemia, myocardial damage, and atrial fibrillation [17, 24]. Hypothyroidism, considering that hormonal therapy requires regular monitoring, represents a crucial complication for many patients. Even the fact of daily morning medication intake is burdensome for patients.

In light of the above, the performance of hemithyroidectomy in unilateral multinodular TG pathology is currently being discussed. The advantage of this volume of surgery is that it theoretically allows for the avoidance of replacement therapy with levothyroxine, and in the event of recurrence, the risk of complications after a repeat operation is reduced, since the contralateral lobe remains untouched during the primary surgery [3].

The aim of the study is evaluate the long-term results of various volumes of surgical intervention for multinodular euthyroid goiter.

Material and methods

281 patients with multinodular euthyroid goiter (MNEG) were studied, who underwent surgical treatment. Of these, 76 (27.1%) patients with bilateral MNEG underwent total thyroidectomy, 72 (25.6%) with bilateral MNEG underwent subtotal thyroidectomy, 35 (12.5%) with bilateral MNEG underwent Dunhill operation (OD), 52 (18.5%) with unilateral MNEG and 46 (16.4%) with nodular euthyroid gland (NEG) underwent hemithyroidectomy. The age of the patients ranged from 20 to 77 years. Among them, 254 (90.4%) were women and 27 (9.6%) were men. Was performed hormones levels TGand pituitary (T4 free and TSH), as well as ultrasound of the TG, and fine-needle aspiration biopsy (FNAB) when necessary.

Statistical analysis For the comparison of continuous variables between independent groups, parametric

and non-parametric statistical approaches were applied as appropriate. When the data met assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances, between-group differences were evaluated using Pearson’s chi-squaredtest(Table 1) and t-Student test (Table 5), originally described by Student for assessing mean differences in normally distributed samples [18].

Results

Let us consider each group of operated patients with MNEG separately. 107 patients with bilateral MNEG were examined, including 72 (67.3%) who underwent subtotal thyroidectomy and 35 (32.7%) who underwent Dunhill operation. The age of the patients ranged from 20 to 70 years. Among them, there were 101 (94.4%) women and 6 (5.6%) men (Table 1). Gender analysis showed that the risk of relapse in women is 3.47 times higher than in men, p value = 0.403.

Table 1.

Characteristics of patients with MNEG who underwent ST and OD

		Young&middle-aged			Elderly		Total	OR	95%CI	P value
		19-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	61-70				
Male	N	-	1	4	-	1	6	3.47	[0.2;64.1]	0.403
	Recurrence	-	-	-	-	-	-			
Female	N	8	20	30	23	20	101	2.40	[0.7;7.7]	0.145
	Recurrence	1	1	4	9	6	21			
Type of surgery	ST	5	10	23	21	13	72	3.44	[0.9;12.4]	0.05*
	Recurrence	1	1	3	8	4	17			
	OD	3	11	11	2	8	35			
	Recurrence	-	-	1	1	2	4			
Duration (years)	up to 5	3	14	8	6	8	39	3.44	[0.9;12.4]	0.05*
	Recurrence	1	-	-	1	1	3			
	6 or >	5	7	26	17	13	68			
	Recurrence	-	1	4	8	5	18			

* Pvalue< 0.05statisticallysignificant; ST - subtotal thyroidectomy; OD - Dunhill operation

With an increase in the volume of surgery, the frequency of MNEG recurrence decreases: after performing ST, it was 23.6% (n=17), and after OD, it was 11.4% (n=4). The Odd ration (OR) of recurrence after ST is 2.4 times higher than after OD, p value = 0.145. Furthermore, the recurrence rate increases with the age of the patients and the duration of follow-up: recurrences are more often observed in patients older than 50 years (34%) and after 6 years of postoperative follow-up (28.1%) (Table 1). Since the development of recurrence requires a certain amount of time, it must be assumed that in patients operated at a young age, unlike

older patients, the possibility of recurrence development exists. Characterizing the recurrent nodules, it should be noted that less than 2 cm in size were observed in 9 (42.8%) of patients, less than 3 cm in 9 (42.8%) of patients, and only in 3 (14.3%) of patients were they larger than 3 cm. The risk of relapse increases after 6 years or more by 3.44 times than in the first 5 years, statistically significant, p value = 0.05. The group of patients who underwent TT included 76 patients with bilateral MNEG, aged 20 to 77 years. Their characteristics by sex, age, duration of follow-up after surgery, and postoperative replacement therapy are shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Characteristics of patients with bilateral MNEG who underwent TT

Age	N	Sex		Duration of follow-up (years)				Hormonal status		
		Male	Female	1-2	3-5	6-10	11 and more	Euthyroid	Hypo Thyroid	Hiper Thyroid
19-30	4		4	3	-	1	-	2	1	1
31-40	13		13	3	4	4	2	7	5	1
41-50	21		21	4	4	10	2	10	10	1
51-60	19	1	18	6	6	7	-	11	7	1
61 and more	19	1	18	5	8	4	3	15	3	1
Total %	76	2 (2.6%)	74 (97.4%)	21(27.6%)	22 (28.9%)	26 (34.2%)	7 (9.2%)	45 (59.2%)	26 (34.2%)	5 (6.6%)

Table 3.

Characteristics of patients with unilateral MNEG who underwent HT

Age (years)	N	Sex		Duration of follow-up (years)			Levothyroxin intake		Hormonal status		HT	
		Male	Female	1-3	4-5	6-10	Done	Not done	Normal	Sub-clin hypothyroid	Left	Right
19-30	10		10	1	7	2	2	8	8	2	4	6
31-40	10	1	9		6	4	1	9	8	2	4	6
41-50	16	4	12		11	5	2	14	14	2	7	9
51-60	10	3	7	1	6	3	3	7	9	1	4	6
61 and more	6	1	5	1	4	1	3	3	3	3	3	3
Total (%)	52	9 (17.3%)	43 (82.7%)	3 (5.8%)	34 (65.4%)	15 (28.8%)	11 (21.2%)	41 (78.8%)	42 (80.7%)	10 (19.2%)	22 (42.3%)	30 (57.7%)

HT – hemithyroidectomy

As seen from Table 2, the predominant majority of examined patients were women (97.4%), aged 41 years and older (75%). The largest number of patients (34.2%) was observed during 6-10 years after the surgical intervention.

More than was evaluated the long-term results of surgical treatment of 52 patients with unilateral MNEG (aged 20 to 65 years). The characteristics of these patients are presented in Table 3.

As shown in Table 3, the predominant majority of patients were women (82.7%), aged 41-50 years (30.8%). Almost all patients (94.2%) were followed up for 4 to 10 years. Two or more nodules or a conglomerate of nodules were located in the right lobe in 57.7% of cases, and in the left lobe in 42.3%.

We studied the long-term outcomes of hemithyroidectomy in 46 patients with NEG (Table 4). Women accounted for 78.3% of them, men – 21.7%.

Table 4

Characteristics of patients with NEG who underwent for hemithyroidectomy

Age	N	Sex		Duration of follow-up, years			Levothyroxine intake		Hormone level		Side of HT	
		M	F	1-3	4-5	6-13	Yes	No	Normal	Hypothyroid	L	R
19-30	9		9		8*	1*	2	7	8	1	4	5
31-40	8	1	7		6	2	2	6	7	1	5	3
41-50	14	5	9	1	12	1	1	13	13	1	6	8
51-60	10	4	6		7	3	2	8	10		5	5
61 and more	5		5		5		2	3	2	3	2	3
Total %	46	10 (21,7)	36 (78,3)	1 (2,2)	38 (82,6)	7 (15,2)	9 (19,6)	37 (80,4)	40 (87)	6 (13)	22 (47,8)	24 (52,2)

* - number of recurrence

Most of patients were aged 41-50 years (30.4%). A solitary nodule was located in the left lobe of the thyroid gland in 47.8% of patients, and in the right lobe in 52.2%. 82.6% of patients were follow-up for 4-5 years after surgery. 87% of all patients were in euthyroid hormonal status, only 13% had subclinical hypothyroidism (TSH up to 10 uIU/mL). Postoperative replacement therapy was received by 9 (19.6%) patients: five of them took levothyroxine -25, four - levothyroxine 50. Among these patients, 55.6% of individuals had lymphoid infiltration of thyroid tissue, hereditary genesis

of the disease was noted in 44.4% of them. Only two young female patients (4.3%) had recurrence nodules measuring 5-7 mm in diameter in the contralateral lobe. Both patients had a hereditary origin of the disease, and the nodules developed in the context of adenomatous goiter. Therefore, hemithyroidectomy for NEG is the optimal volume of surgery.

A comparison of replacement therapy levels in MNEG patients who underwent various volumes of surgery is presented in Table 5.

Table 5.

Levels of replacement therapy in MNEG patients who underwent various volumes of surgical intervention

Patientgroup	Levothyroxinedose, mcg	P(TT)	P(ST+OD)	P(HT-NEG)
TT, n=76	120,1±3,9 (50-200)			
ST+OD, n=107	99,6±4,9 (50-200)	p<0,001		
HT-MNEG, n=52	40,9±5,1 (25-75)	p<0,001	p<0,001	
HT – NEG, n=46	36,1±4,4(25-50)	p<0,001	p<0,001	p<0,05

TT- total thyroidectomy; ST - subtotal thyroidectomy; OD - Dunhill operation; HT - hemithyroidectomy

As seen from Table 5, the highest doses of levothyroxine are necessarily taken by patients who underwent TT, and approximately 2.5 times lower doses are taken by patients who underwent ST and OD, and three times lower doses are taken by patients who underwent hemithyroidectomy comparatively.

Discussion

Lin YS et al. compared four different volumes of surgical intervention (total thyroidectomy, Dunhill operation, subtotal thyroidectomy, and hemithyroidectomy) for multinodular goiter. The recurrence rate was highest with ST (21.6%), but only 1.8% of patients required a repeat operation [25]. According to the data from this study, only 5% of patients with goiter required repeat surgery [31]. In our study, only 4 (5.5%) patients who underwent ST and had recurrence were presumed to require a repeat surgical intervention. Indications for surgery were: symptoms of compression, nodule size greater than 3 cm, conclusion of cytological examination corresponding to category *Betesda IV*. Recurrences that developed after OD were clinically insignificant. In our study, the role of a hereditary factor in the development of recurrence was confirmed: cases of repeated TG involvement were noted among 14 (66.7%) of patients with recurrence. Other authors, evaluating family history, did not find significant differences between the overall examined group and the group of individuals with MNEG recurrences [26]. Literature data on the role of replacement therapy in the development of nodular goiter recurrences are contradictory. Some authors believe that patients with MNEG require careful and individually selected replacement therapy in the postoperative period, since postoperative hypothyroidism is the driving force behind the development of nodular goiter recurrences [7, 29]. Other authors report that levothyroxine replacement or suppression therapy does not effectively prevent recurrence in patients with multinodular euthyroid goiter [27, 19]. Postoperative replacement therapy was prescribed to all patients who underwent ST and OD. As a result of the examination, the patients were divided into 3 groups. The first group – 60 (56.1%) patients - took levothyroxine in a replacement dose, regularly attended consultation with the treating physician. The second group – 31 (28.9%) patients - did not take levothyroxine, did not attend the necessary consultations, and did not regularly check the TSH level, due to the fact that their TSH levels were above the reference range during the examination. The third group consisted of 16 (14.9%) patients who took levothyroxine irregularly, with interruptions and without controlling the TSH level. Among

patients with MNEG recurrences, 33.3% were individuals who took levothyroxine in the required dose, 66.7% were those who did not take or took levothyroxine in an insufficient dose; 4 (19.1%) patients took it in an insufficient dose, being in a state of hypothyroidism. The literature emphasizes the role of lymphocytic infiltration in the development of postoperative hypothyroidism and MNEG recurrence [12, 15]. After all, this activity reflects the activity of immune disorders that are a risk factor for the development of postoperative hypothyroidism, leading to recurrence [15]. In our study, lymphocytic infiltration of the TG tissue was observed in 8 (38.1%) patients with recurrences.

Analysis of the hormonal background in patients who underwent TT, revealed that 59.2% who were taking levothyroxine were in a euthyroid state; 40.8 % of patients were not compensated: some of them did not take levothyroxine at all or took it irregularly, others took it in an inadequate dose (34.2% were hypothyroid, 6.6% were hyperthyroid). In this regard, when complaints were presented, they reported a mass of complaints: weakness, bone pain, dry skin, hair loss, palpitations, irritability, etc. The above indicates that patients in the postoperative period irregularly and reluctantly visit the endocrinologist and the operating surgeon.

In patients with multinodular euthyroid goiter who present with bilateral nodules, total thyroidectomy is frequently recommended to minimize the risk of recurrence and to avoid the need for re-operation [4]. However, there are patients with asymmetric multinodular goiter, in whom several nodules or a conglomerate of nodules are located in one lobe and a share of the isthmus. Recurrence rates after hemithyroidectomy for multinodular goiter have been reported to range from 5% to 34%, and recurrence is strongly associated with the length of postoperative follow-up [22]. Recurrence can be subclinical, which occurs in most cases and is determined by ultrasound as new foci (more 5 mm) in the contralateral lobe of the thyroid gland even after primary surgery, or it can be clinically obvious in the form of a palpable nodule. Currently, hemithyroidectomy in this group of patients is a controversial and relevant issue. The reason for its performance is the low recurrence rate and postoperative hypothyroidism (23% and 31%, respectively) [23].

In our research postoperative replacement therapy was received by 11 (21.2%) patients with unilateral MNEG, 5 of whom received levothyroxine dose of 50 µg, 5 received 25 µg, and 1 received 75 µg. Of these, 72.7% had lymphocytic infiltration of the TG tissue and

63.6% had a hereditary gene for the disease. Postoperative hypothyroidism was found in 21.2% of patients, which is consistent with the data of other authors [1, 9, 13]. Follow-up duration of 6 (11.5%) patients developed recurrence, and in all cases, a nodule with a diameter up to 1cm emerged, with a subclinical nature, revealed by ultrasound. Recurrences developed more often at a young age (up to 40 years), after 6 years of surgery in patients with a hereditary gene for the disease and those in a state of subclinical hypothyroidism. The recurrence rate after hemithyroidectomy for unilateral MNEG and after the Dunhill operation is practically identical (11.5% and 11.4%), but in the former case, a larger volume of functioning TG tissue is preserved.

Thus, in patients with nodular and unilateral multinodular euthyroid goiter who underwent hemithyroidectomy, the following was observed low recurrence rates (4.3% and 11.5%, respectively). The incidence of postoperative hypothyroidism compensated by replacement therapy after hemithyroidectomy for NEG and MNEG is 19.6% and 21.2%, respectively, which is consistent with data from other authors [6, 7, 8, 10]. The quality of life was much better for patients after hemithyroidectomy, than for patients who underwent radical surgeries: 84.8% of patients with NEG and 78.8% of patients with unilateral MNEG did not require burdensome hormone therapy. However, patients with hypothyroidism need a low level of postoperative replacement therapy. A comparison of levothyroxine levels taken by patients with NEG and MNEG after hemithyroidectomy revealed a non-significant ($p > 0.05$) difference between the groups, consistent to $36.1 \pm 4.4 \mu\text{g}$ and $40.9 \pm 5.1 \mu\text{g}$, respectively. Risk factors for the development of recurrence of MNEG include the patient's young age, the duration of follow-up, the absence of replacement therapy, the presence of a hereditary genesis of the disease and lymphoid infiltration. Factors predisposing to the development of postoperative hypothyroidism include lymphoid infiltration of the glandular tissue, the duration of follow-up hereditary genesis of the disease. Obtained risk factors of recurrence and postoperative hypothyroidism the same this results of many authors [6, 8, 11, 16].

Conclusions

The frequency of MNEG recurrences after subtotal thyroidectomy was 23.6%, after the Dunhill operation was 11.4%, and after hemithyroidectomy was 11.5%. The quality of life of patients after hemithyroidectomy was significantly better: 78.8% of individuals with MNEG did not require the burden of constant hormonal therapy. Patients in this group with hypothyroidism received a minimally reduced dose of levothyroxine compared to patients who underwent TT, ST, and OD ($40.9 \pm 5.1 \text{ mcg}$ ($p < 0.001$)). Postoperative replacement therapy is insufficiently effective: 66.7% of MNEG patients with recurrences who underwent ST either did not take levothyroxine at all or took it in an insufficient dose, and 66.7% of individuals with recurrences after unilateral MNEG were in a state of subclinical hypothyroidism. Risk factors for the development of postoperative MNEG hypothyroidism include a hereditary gene for the disease, lymphocytic infiltration

of the TG tissue, and duration of follow-up. Risk factors for the development of MNEG recurrence include young age of the patient, presence of replacement therapy, presence of a hereditary gene for the disease, duration of follow-up, and presence of lymphocytic infiltration. Performing hemithyroidectomy for NEG and unilateral MNEG is the optimal volume of surgery. However, the choice of this procedure for unilateral MNEG is a joint decision between the surgeon and the patient, made, taking into account risk factors for recurrence and postoperative hypothyroidism are determined individually for each patient.

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